

D1.2 Data Management Plan

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List of definitions and acronyms

Acronym	Expansion
CC	Creative Commons
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
Data	Information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. The focus is on research data that is available in digital form. (European Commission, 2016b)
Dataset (DS)	A grouping of data
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
Metadata	A description of data
Open Access	Access that is free to all and free of any restrictions
Open Data	Data that can be freely used, shared and built on by anyone for any purpose
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
PPSR	Public Participation in Scientific Research
Repository	A location in which data is stored or managed
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The ECS Data Management Plan (DMP) is Deliverable 1.2 (D1.2) from the EU-funded project European Citizen Science, grant agreement (GA) nr. 101058509. This deliverable introduces the first version of the DMP. The DMP describes the types of data that will be generated or collected during the project, the way in which the ECS consortium will manage the datasets that will emerge from the project (what datasets the consortium is aiming to preserve and in which format), and how best practice in terms of metadata and archiving will be used to ensure that the data will be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) for other potential users. Such users include

researchers and practitioners in the field of citizen science, as well as any other interested party.

The DMP is a living document and the datasets referred to in this document are drafted during the first project stages. This document thus reflects the project partners' initial plans toward developing the overall project's datasets. The DMP will see updates elaborating on the collected datasets, as well as reflecting changes in the project.

The leading frameworks for data management in ECS are the GDPR to protect personal data and the FAIR principles to handle non-personal research data in the project and facilitate data re-use.

Introduction

The purpose of the preliminary Data Management Plan (DMP) for the ECS project is to ensure GDPR compliance and to outline the details and procedures of how the project partners will handle data generated in the project according to the relevant aspects of making data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), including what data the project will generate, whether and how it will be made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated, as well as facilitate the potential re-use of the data collected and processed within the project.

The DMP is a living document and the datasets referred to in this document are drafted during the first project stages. This document thus reflects the project partners' initial plans toward developing the overall project's datasets. The DMP will be updated, revised and elaborated on the collected datasets, as well as reflecting changes in the project and approach. Updates are planned at the end of each reporting period and when necessary.

The structure of this document follows the DMP template for projects funded under Horizon Europe.

Data Management Plan Objectives

This document is the first iteration of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the ECS project and is part of WP1 "Project management and coordination". The DMP identifies the data and datasets that will be collected, processed, generated and used during the ECS project with respect to each work package, and defines each dataset's purpose and life cycle. This document and its updates will include up-to-date information on whether and how research data will be exploited, made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and securely preserved for the long-term.

As stated in the Programme Guide for HORIZON (European Commission 2022), DMPs are a cornerstone for responsible management of research outputs, notably data – they are also mandatory in Horizon Europe for projects that generate and or re-use data. Good and responsible data management makes project work more efficient and contributes to safeguarding information and increasing the value of the data among the beneficiaries themselves and others, during and after the research. Therefore, writing a DMP is a key part of good data management and of the methodology of the project (ibid.).

According to the Guidelines on FAIR Data management in Horizon 2020 (European Commission, 2016a), as part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR), a DMP should include information on the following:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project,
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated,
- which methodology and standards will be applied,
- whether data will be shared/made open access, and
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

Therefore, the objectives of this DMP are:

- to identify the datasets that the ECS project will produce,
- to define how these datasets will be made FAIR,
- to define the allocation of resources (costs and responsibility) for data management during and after the project, and
- to define procedures for data security (including data recovery as well as safe storage) during the project and for long term preservation.

The DMP should contribute to maximise the impact of ECS, ensure a high level of data quality and accessibility for final users and stakeholders, and allow the application of data analytics techniques.

As a living document, the DMP will be regularly updated and revised to account for project developments. An updated version of the Data Management Plan will be released if other kinds of data will be generated/collected, if changes in consortium policies or in consortium composition occur, and if any other external factors affect the validity of the present DMP.

A key element of sustainable data management, the DMP outlines what, and how, data will be collected, processed and/or generated, which methodology and standards will be applied, whether data will be shared/made open access and also how data will be curated and preserved during and after the end of the project. It provides guidelines, answers to issues, and presents the approach that the ECS project will adopt with respect to the management and protection of data. Legal and ethical issues related to the project's collecting and/or processing of personal data are identified and practically considered, taking into consideration the different methods by which data are collected (interview, online survey, workshop, questionnaire, etc.).

With regards to personal data, the consortium shall ensure that data on individuals are transmitted and used in a secure environment; that the use of the data complies with ethical and legal requirements (including signed informed consent and applicable data protection laws); and that the use of both existing and new data is agreed with the data owner/data provider. Data records containing personal data are managed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).

It is the responsibility of every partner to notify the coordinator of changes in the data they are collecting during the project.

Project Background

Project details

Project full title and acronym: European Citizen Science (ECS)

Grant Agreement no.: 101058509

Call: HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01

Topic: HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-60 (A capacity-building and brokering network to make citizen science an integral part of the European Research Area)

Type of action: CSA

Start date: 01/08/2022

End date: 31/07/2026

Number of participants in the Consortium: 12 beneficiaries and 9 Affiliated Entities

Project description

The overall objective of ECS is to widen and strengthen the European Citizen Science community through capacity building and awareness raising activities such as the creation of a European Citizen Science Academy and the establishment of a network of 28 ECS Ambassadors. ECS will capitalise on EU-funded actions such as the [eu-citizen.science platform](#) and [Cos4Cloud](#) to support links and collaboration between members of the European Citizen Science community, who will be involved in the co-design and co-creation of a large variety of services, strategic priorities, training opportunities and policy recommendations. A key focus is on inclusivity, which will be achieved through dedicated actions such as engaging libraries affiliated to the Public Libraries 2030 network to attract underrepresented publics, as well as ad-hoc support to countries/regions lacking citizen science networks, platforms and policy recognition.

ECS will create extensive capacity building opportunities by engaging in particular excellent researchers in a variety of disciplines, for example through the involvement of the Marie Curie Alumni Association, and emerging Horizon Europe Missions, Clusters, and wider ERA activities, to allow easy access for newcomers in citizen science activities. ECS is committed to push modern science towards open science as its modus operandi by providing open collaborative spaces where citizen scientists can familiarise with the concept of "open and FAIR data with open and FAIR tools" and get actively engaged, while connecting with existing e-infrastructures such as EOSC through the collaborative development of data/metadata services. The engagement of the Global Citizen Science Partnership will guarantee wide international cooperation. These efforts will result in a number of key scientific, societal and policy impacts which will strongly contribute to securing Europe's global position as a leader in citizen science throughout the entire research and innovation system.

The six specific objectives of ECS are:

- **Objective 1:** Empower the European citizen science community through co-design and co-creation
- **Objective 2:** Strengthen the links and collaboration between existing citizen science initiatives
- **Objective 3:** Increase the participation of citizens from all walks of life in citizen science through an inclusive approach
- **Objective 4:** Build the capacity to conduct excellent research and innovation through citizen science
- **Objective 5:** Raise awareness, support and mainstream citizen science among new actors, new territories and scientific fields
- **Objective 6:** Better align data infrastructures to the needs of citizen science, and improve open science practices employed by citizen science initiatives

Project Consortium

The ECS consortium is composed of 12 Beneficiaries and 9 Affiliated Entities, members of ECSA, covering 15 countries. The consortium is truly interdisciplinary and complementary in terms of expertise and is a perfect fit to reach the objectives and impact required by this call. The beneficiaries unite expertise in citizen science (ECSA, UP, MfN, Ibercivis, SfC, CSIC) and co-creation (SD, SfC), platform and community development (Ibercivis, CSIC, ECSA), coupled with experience in inclusion and diversity (PL2030, SfC, SD, ZSI) as well as leading expertise in data infrastructure and ethics (CSIC). All of the above combined with recognised

competence in impact assessment (ZSI) and a huge geographical coverage (MCAA, ECSA, PL2030) makes the ECS team a perfect fit for successful project implementation.

In addition to the 12 partners, ECS consortium consists of nine ECSA Affiliated Entities. The nine Affiliated Entities and NILU (due to administrative reasons, NILU is included in the proposal as partner but their role is the same as that of Affiliated Entities) represent a diversity of stakeholders such as SMEs, NGO, public body, museum, research organisation and university – all with expertise in citizen science. They come from 10 different countries and were selected through a public call for ECSA members.

Table 1. Participants in the ECS Consortium – 12 beneficiaries and 9 Affiliated Entities.

Acronym	Role	Participant	Country	Logo
ECSA	COO	European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) ECSA E.V.	Germany	European Citizen Science Association
W2L	AE	Web2Learn	Greece	Web2Learn Open, social learning
ULEI	AE	Universiteit Leiden	Netherlands	citizen science lab
ULHT/CeD	AE	Cooperativa de Formação e Animação Cultural CRL	Portugal	UNIVERSIDADE LUSÓFONA
TCD	AE	The Provost, Fellows, Foundation Scholars & the Other Members of Board, of the College of the Holy & Undivided Trinity of Queen Elizabeth Near Dublin (Trinity College)	Ireland	Trinity College Dublin Coláiste na Tríonóide, Baile Átha Cliath The University of Dublin
NORDECO	AE	Nordisk Fond for Miljø og Udvikling	Denmark	NORDECO Nordic Agency for Development and Ecology
MOFET INSTITUTE	AE	The MOFET Institute - The School For The Research And Development Of Programs In Teacher Training And Education At Colleges	Israel	The MOFET Institute Research, Curriculum and Program Development for Teacher Educators
FGC	AE	Fondazione Grosseto Cultura	Italy	MUSEO DI STORIA NATURALE DELLA MAREMMA
IGN	AE	Institute of Geonics Of The AS CR, V.V.I.	Czech Republic	ÚGN

BWI	AE	Blue World Institute	Croatia	
SD	BEN	Stickydot SRL	Belgium	
SfC	BEN	Science for Change, SL	Spain	
IBERCIVIS	BEN	Fundación Ibercivis	Spain	
CSIC	BEN	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)	Spain	
MFN	BEN	Museum für Naturkunde - Leibniz-Institut für Evolutions- und Biodiversitätsforschung, Berlin	Germany	
ZSI	BEN	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation GMBH	Austria	
MCAA	BEN	Marie Curie Alumni Association	Belgium	
PL2030	BEN	Public Libraries 2030	Belgium	
UP	BEN	Université Paris Cité	France	

NILU	BEN	Nilu Stiftelsen Norsk Institutt For Luftforskning (NILU)	Norway	
NMC	BEN	Nordlicht Management Consultant	Germany	

Project Work Packages

The ECS project comprises nine WPs understood as building blocks that are structured to deliver the outputs efficiently, ensuring the highest return on the resources that are invested (see Figure 1 below). All WPs are closely linked, thus running throughout the entire duration of the project.

List of WPs:

- WP1** – Project management and coordination
- WP2** – Strengthening links and collaboration
- WP3** – Enhancing digital skills for FAIR and open science communities
- WP4** – European citizen science academy
- WP5** – Boosting inclusion and diversity for mainstreaming citizen science
- WP6** – Communication and outreach for the global citizen science community
- WP7** – Policy impacts and recommendations
- WP8** – Impact Pathways Assessment
- WP9** – Ethics requirements

Figure 1. ECS work package structure.

WP1 is dedicated to project management and coordination with the EC. WP2 and WP3 focus on collaboration and openness aspects of the ECS community, to lay the ground for its wider activities. WP2 has a greater focus on bringing together the European Citizen Science community, including enhancing the online services of the eu-citizen.science platform and supporting networks Europe-wide. WP3 focuses on enhancing digital skills and data services towards FAIR and open practices. Both WP2 and WP3 are supported by a dedicated effort to provide training and capacity building through the European Citizen Science Academy in WP4. To ensure inclusion and diversity in the process of mainstreaming citizen science, WP5 is dedicated to this mission. WP6 is aimed at communication and outreach, and international collaboration, while WP7 is dedicated to policy impacts and uptake of emerging recommendations at national, European, and global levels. WP8 closely monitors the envisioned impact pathways of all WPs, providing evidence for the achievement of the expected outputs and outcomes. Finally, WP9 is dedicated to ethics requirements. A detailed description of each WP and associated tasks is provided in the Description of Action.

1. Data Summary

The ECS project is expected to generate a substantial amount of data of various types. This section covers the re-use of any existing data, the types and formats of data generated or re-used by the project, the purpose of data generation and re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project, the expected size of data generated or re-used and their provenance, and to whom ECS project data might be useful outside of the project. Information in this section has been provided by WP leaders for each WP in the project in consultation with some task leaders.

The overall objective of ECS is to widen and strengthen the European Citizen Science community through capacity building and awareness raising activities. Therefore, many ECS (participatory) activities will involve participants who will be invited to answer to online surveys, evaluation questionnaires, as well as join co-design, co-creation and co-development participatory workshops (online and face-to face) at various stages of the ECS development. The main objective of these activities is for participants to share their vision, needs, expectations and ideas towards the development of a European Citizen Science community.

The ECS project will collect or generate data from questionnaires, interviews, participatory workshops, discussions, reflection and learning sessions involving stakeholders and citizens that participate voluntarily in the project. The project will follow the principle of making data 'as open as possible as closed as necessary'. Any data collection, processing and storage activities, procedures and tools will be in line with the personal data protection and intellectual property rights of the European Union, as defined by the European Commission. ECS will not be collecting any 'special categories' of personal data as defined by Article 9 of the GDPR Regulation (EU) 2016/679. Formalised questionnaires and personal data will be stored at the local level.

Overall, the ECS project plans to (potentially) reuse open research data from other projects and initiatives such as outputs from the CS Track project, existing data from citizen observatories and tools and services developed in the framework of the Cos4Cloud project, an open repository file about existing training resources from the TIME4CS project, or the declaration developed within the CS-SDG project. A subsection on the eu-citizen.science platform, which will be further developed during the ECS project, is included below.

Table 2 and Table 3 below provide an overview of the data and datasets that ECS plans to reuse and collect respectively, as of January 2023. These tables include a description of the data and its purpose (alignment with the objectives of the project); the types, formats and expected size of the data; the relevance or utility outside the project; its provenance (if it is reused) and its storage period (if it is generated). A subsection on the types of data that may be collected has been added for clarification. ECS will follow open standard formats and coherent name filing conventions to endorse the FAIR principles of data sharing as explained in more detail in section 2.

The eu-citizen.science platform

The eu-citizen.science platform was created and developed during the EU-Citizen.Science project that ran from 2019-2021. The overall vision for the eu-citizen.science platform was to aid the mainstreaming of citizen science in Europe, such that it becomes an appreciated and widely established means for the democratisation of science.

ECS will exploit the eu-citizen.science platform, thus it will make use of its existing database schema to use data about projects, resources, training, events and platforms on citizen science. This information is stored in a PostgreSQL database and publicly available through both the platform and existing API. New data will be added and merged in the existing database. Metadata on the eu-citizen.science platform is following standards (e.g [PPSR Core on Citizen Science projects](#)) which allow the interoperability with similar platforms. User data (personal profiles) are also stored complying with GDPR.

The eu-citizen.Science platform code is [available on GitHub](#) under European Union Public License 1.2 (EUPL). This is a copyleft free/open source software licence created on the initiative of and approved by the European Commission. Information about the Permissions, Limitations and Conditions of this licence as well as the licence itself can be found [in the LICENSE file of the repository](#).

Type of Data

The following type of data may be collected and documented. This classification has been directly taken from the Data Management Plan created by the TIME4CS project (Iasillo & Spera 2022).

- **Observational:** data captured through observation of an activity and/or a behaviour in real-time (and, therefore, usually irreplaceable). The collection usually may require human observation, surveys and instruments to record the information.
- **Experimental:** data obtained in controlled situations through the active intervention of researchers, who design an activity (called experiment) to collect data. They can be reproduced if needed, but it may be expensive.
- **Simulation:** data generated reproducing a real-world system, normally used to determine what would happen in certain conditions.
- **Derived or Compiled:** data derived upon transformation of existing data sets to create new data. They can be reproduced if lost, but it is very time-consuming and it could be expensive.
- **Reference or Canonical:** it refers to data used to categorise and/or classify other data. They could be static or changing over time.
- **Event-related:** data collected during events. As they are real-time events, they are irreplaceable. They can include personal data of participants, and GDPR will be applied.

It is worth pointing out that these categories can overlap, and data can belong to more than one category depending on the specificities of the data itself (e.g. event-related data could also be considered observational data upon certain conditions).

Table 2. Data and datasets re-used for each ECS WP as of January 2023.

WP	Reuse of existing data and reasons for it	Types and formats to generate or re-use	Purpose of the data generation or re-use	Expected size of the data	Origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used	Data utility (usefulness), outside the project
General	Outputs from the CS Track project might be re-used, e.g. technical knowledge openly available on GitHub or on other repositories.	Technical knowledge from CS Track can be used to generate a database of information on citizen science projects contained in platforms and websites. Format: most likely .XLSX and .CSV	Algorithms can be used to get information for websites and to extract information from the data extracted to get a better understanding of the citizen science landscape and available information about citizen science.	It will vary depending on the type of data. Unknown at this stage.	Both, re-used (algorithms and crawler) and generated (database using the crawler and algorithms).	In case the dataset with information on citizen science projects in Europe is analysed to get an overview or provide new classifications, results could be relevant to citizen science practitioners and coordinators, academics, and policymakers.
WP1	Data collected during the ECS proposal preparation and GA preparation will be re-used for project management and coordination overall (WP1).	Generate contact lists for internal communicational, project outputs (e.g. deliverables, reports and presentations) and all data needed for financial and technical reporting. Formats: .XLSX, .DOCX, .PPTX, .PDF, Photo Format, Video Format.	Ensure an efficient communication flow within the consortium. Share project results publicly beyond the consortium. Ensure proper administrative and financial project management.	It will vary depending on the type of data but they are expected to be in the (low) hundreds of MB, while potential video files can be in GB.	Both, generated and re-used, but mostly generated.	Public project outputs such as deliverables, presentations, and reports about the project or activities carried out in the project can be relevant to the wider citizen science community, and to other organisations implementing or planning a project with similar characteristics.
WP2	The database of the eu-citizen.science platform , which is owned by project partners, will be re-used. The platform	Registration forms and personal data necessary to ensure representativeness and inclusion in co-creation groups.	Ensure representativeness and inclusion in the co-creation groups. Strengthen and expand identified communities.	It will vary depending on the type of data and the number of participants.	Both, generated and re-used, but mostly generated.	As most of the data is generated through co-creation sessions with Europe's own citizen science community, it is the community itself that is

WP	Reuse of existing data and reasons for it	Types and formats to generate or re-use	Purpose of the data generation or re-use	Expected size of the data	Origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used	Data utility (usefulness), outside the project
	code, which is licensed under EU PL, will be further developed.	Interviews with stakeholders, groups of interest, survey data, observational data, and workshop data. Development code and documentation associated with digital products and services. Formats: DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, json, CSV/XLS, HTML, or other Web coding language, data analysis coding (python/R), extracts from Miro Board and other collaboration tools, (PDF, JPEG).	Ensure the success of the co-creation process. Develop and implement the services required by the community. Enhancing synergies between projects, institutions and communities. Facilitate communication channels and identify common interests and best practices.	They can be in the order of hundreds of MBs.		primarily interested in the outcome data. Any national, regional or local citizen science platform. Researchers, project managers and institutions that usually work with digital citizen science services.
WP3	Re-using existing data from Citizen Observatories in training sessions (T3.2 and T3.3). Also re-using data from services and tools developed in Cos4Cloud.	Interviews with stakeholders, survey data, observational data, and workshop data. Generate registration data to understand who has attended our workshop/training programs. Generate open and closed data files for the purpose of training provision. Metadata and analytical data from online training events and	Training events and capacity building sessions. Training materials for enhancing digital skills for implementing data acquisition infrastructures. Facilitate the reuse and the interoperability of developed products.	It will vary depending on the type of data and the number of participants. They can be in the order of hundreds of MBs.	Mostly reused. Generated by Citizen Observatories	Training materials for the community interested in developing methods of analysis and visualisation and for people interested in data acquisition systems (mobile apps or DIY instruments). Training materials for communities interested in contributing to citizen science projects with code.

WP	Reuse of existing data and reasons for it	Types and formats to generate or re-use	Purpose of the data generation or re-use	Expected size of the data	Origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used	Data utility (usefulness), outside the project
		activities that are generated during training. Formats: DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, json, CSV/XLS, HTML, or other Web coding language, data analysis coding (python/R), extracts from Miro Board and other collaboration tools, (PDF, JPEG).				
WP4	Using a repository file created by TIME4CS (open data repository file)- a deliverable- about existing training resources. This will help us understand existing training materials, provide us information about who are citizen science educators and trainers, and understand what are the gaps in training material for citizen science.	Survey data, compiled data, event-related data will be generated to understand for example the needs of citizen science educators/trainers, contact citizen science educators and trainers, and the delivery of workshops. Metadata and analytical data from online training events and activities that are generated during training. Generate open and closed data files for the purpose of training provision. Contact list data- to form networks- e.g. contact details	Reuse of data in a list of training materials on citizen science that already exist. We will continue to add to this list and generate data about training materials. This will enable us to make them available, with the permission of the author of the training material to publish them on the eu-citizen.science platform to make them accessible to the community- and also inform us about training material gaps to inform the	It will vary depending on the type of data. Surveys, mailing lists and contact information is likely to total in hundreds of MB, while analytical information can be in GB.	Both generated and re-used.	Sharing of these training modules (open data) on the eu-citizen.science platform. Future projects who want to utilise the contacts for training. ECSA, for the purpose of future activities of the European Citizen Science Academy.

WP	Reuse of existing data and reasons for it	Types and formats to generate or re-use	Purpose of the data generation or re-use	Expected size of the data	Origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used	Data utility (usefulness), outside the project
		<p>of individuals that match our audience of interest, for network of citizen science educators and trainers and of MCSA and ERC grantees that have used CS. Network - closed/we will ask permission from these individuals to create a network. List of participants/names of this network will not be disclosed and will be managed according to GDPR.</p> <p>Registration forms- personal data such as names and email addresses will only be retained to 1) contact individuals if they would like to be part of a network/ fill out a survey) 2) if they allow us to re-contact them or add them to a listserv for the purpose of a network. This data will remain closed to us (managers of the network for the moment) and to the participants of the network. Information from the</p>	<p>development of new training material.</p> <p>Data generation will be used to gather information and create a network of citizen science educators/trainers and researchers that are part of the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA).</p> <p>Demographic data of the workshop will be generated to understand the reach of the audience. This will be useful not only to understand our reach for inclusivity purposes, but also to report on our task impact (e.g. number of researchers we have reached). For registration forms data collected during workshops; identify audience of workshops (open data, aggregation of data for statistics), number of people that attended (open data, aggregation of data for</p>			

WP	Reuse of existing data and reasons for it	Types and formats to generate or re-use	Purpose of the data generation or re-use	Expected size of the data	Origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used	Data utility (usefulness), outside the project
		registration form will also be used to understand the reach of audience/statistical measure/analysis (open data): number of people, affiliation and demographic data for inclusivity purposes. Format: DOCX, XLS/HTML, extracts from Miro Board and/or other collaborative tools (e.g. Slido).	statistics), email address for communication purposes and invitation (closed data). Metadata will assist in the understanding of patterns of use of the material and improve the provision of training.			
WP5	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
WP6	The ECS project has taken over the social media accounts and newsletter used and set up by the EU-Citizen.Science project. This includes Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and a newsletter in mailchimp.	To generate contact lists for the newsletter and registrations to events and workshops. To disseminate and promote the project achievements. Formats: PDF, JPEG, PNG or other image formats, Audio files [mp3 / mp4], XLS/ HTML, or other web coding language, extracts from collaboration tools (PDF, JPEG), audio recordings.	To ensure the flow of communication. To disseminate and promote the project.	It will vary depending on the type of data but they are expected to be in the (low) hundreds of MB, while potential video files can be in GB.	Both generated and re-used.	Public project outputs such as deliverables, presentations, reports, communication and dissemination activities carried out in the project. Consortium members. Participants of ECS initiatives. The citizen science community. Other organisations implementing or planning a project with similar characteristics.

WP	Reuse of existing data and reasons for it	Types and formats to generate or re-use	Purpose of the data generation or re-use	Expected size of the data	Origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used	Data utility (usefulness), outside the project
WP7	Re-using existing data from the declaration of the CS-SDG project.	We will conduct a national stakeholder mapping exercise to identify opportunities and gaps for developing links with CS and Open Science. We will use observed, derived, event-related data collected via workshops on Miro (for example) and stored in the form of spreadsheets, forms, metadata in CSV and spreadsheet formats.	The data generated will strengthen the recognition of CS as a policy-making tool and a valuable research approach for scientific excellence and sustainable development in Europe.	It will vary depending on the type of data. They can be in the order of hundreds of MBs.	Both generated and re-used.	The (European) Citizen Science Community. Policymakers in, across, and beyond Europe.
WP8		Interviews with stakeholders, survey data, observational data, and workshop data. Formats: DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, Audio files [mp3 / mp4], XLS/ HTML, or other Web coding language, extracts from Miro Board and other collaboration tools (PDF, JPEG), audio recordings.	Evaluation and impact assessment; gaining insights on citizen science and how it is evolving in Europe; assessment of the specific measures provided by ECS.	It will vary depending on the type of data but they are expected to be in the hundreds of MB, while potential video files can be in GB.	Both, generated and re-used, but mostly generated.	The data will be mostly relevant for the project evaluation; it could be useful for other projects, organisations or individual researchers doing research on citizen science, especially those with a strong focus on impact assessment.

Table 3. Data and data sets collected for each ECS WP as of January 2023.

WP and partner responsible for the data, activity of data collection	Short data description, aim of the data and relevance for the project	Type of data	Data format	Reuse of any existing data	Relevance outside the project	Expected size	Storage period
WP1 (ECSA) Project partners	This dataset consists of consortium members and members of the Advisory Board. It includes mailing lists for internal communication.	Observational, Derived or compiled	.XLSX	No existing data has been re-used.	N/A, this data is confidential.	-10 KB	Lifetime of the project (including final review period)
WP1 (ECSA) Project management (administrative and financial)	Data related to financial aspects of the project (e.g. cost declarations) and technical project implementation (meeting minutes, reports, presentations)	Observational, Derived or compiled, Event-related	.XLSX .DOCX .PPTX .PDF Photo Format Video Format	Data collected during the stage of project proposal might be used	N/A, this data is confidential.	MBs or GB	(Financial) record-keeping for up to 5 years after the project end; all other information for the lifetime of the project +2 years in case of a review
WP2 (IBERCIVIS) Co-creation networking activities	This dataset corresponds to the outputs of the co-creation (T2.2, T2.3) and networking (T2.4) activities.	Observational, Event-related	.DOCX .PDF .CSV .TXT Extracts from Miro Board, padlet and others collaboration platforms.	Data of previous co-creation activities.	Citizen science community requirements for digital platforms.	MBs or GB	Lifetime of the project

WP and partner responsible for the data, activity of data collection	Short data description, aim of the data and relevance for the project	Type of data	Data format	Reuse of any existing data	Relevance outside the project	Expected size	Storage period
WP2 (IBERCIVIS) Platform code	This dataset corresponds to the code of the ECS platform.	Software code	.TXT	Some code			
WP2 (ECSA) Community engagement events	This dataset consists of: event and participant data of ECS-organised community engagement events, feedback and participant input and feedback	Observational, Event-related	.DOCX .XLSX .PPTX .PDF Photo Format Video Format Audio format Extracts from Miro Board, padlet	Data of existing events (date, location, agenda) might be used as inspiration to organise project events. Documentation of ECS events is original data produced and collected by the project.	Outputs of community engagement events such as recordings of the events made publicly available might be useful to the general public and the citizen science community.	Several GB, depending on how many video recordings this includes	Data from participants max. during the lifetime of the project Published data (video recordings on YouTube) beyond the lifetime of the project
WP2 (SD) ECS Collaboration Group	This dataset consists of names/acronyms of projects as well as names and email addresses of project representatives participating in the monthly ECS Collaboration Group meetings	Observational, Event-related	.DOCX .PDF .XLSX .PPTX	Not initially. Bibliography on the topic.	The data obtained will allow an analysis on how to improve the relationships and collaborations between different stakeholders of the citizen science	Several MB.	Lifetime of the project

WP and partner responsible for the data, activity of data collection	Short data description, aim of the data and relevance for the project	Type of data	Data format	Reuse of any existing data	Relevance outside the project	Expected size	Storage period
					community in the EU.		
WP3 (CSIC) Enhancing digital skills for implementing data acquisition and data analysis infrastructures	Participant data of ECS-organised training events, face-to-face or online, including engagement, feedback, and metadata about the use of training material. We also plan on organising a datathon and hackathon.	Derived or compiled, Event Related	DOCX/ODT, PDF, JPEG, json, CSV/XLS, HTML, or other Web coding language, data analysis coding (python/R), extracts from Miro Board and other collaboration tools, (PDF, JPEG).	Use of existing mailing lists and networks and use of information in other projects or networks	Community interested in developing methods of analysis and visualisation and for people interested in data acquisition systems (mobile apps. Communities interested in contributing code to citizen science projects.	Several MB for each event, likely to be GB at the end of the project	Beyond the project, for the operations of the European Citizen Science Academy
WP4 (UP)	Participant data of ECS-organised training event, face-to-face or online, including engagement, feedback, and metadata about the use of training material	Observational, Event-related, Metadata	Spreadsheet, forms, metadata in CSV, spreadsheet formats	Use of existing mailing lists and networks	Pattern of behaviour of learners	Several MB for each event, likely to be GB at the end of the project	Lifetime of the project

WP and partner responsible for the data, activity of data collection	Short data description, aim of the data and relevance for the project	Type of data	Data format	Reuse of any existing data	Relevance outside the project	Expected size	Storage period
WP4 (UP)	Network and Community of practice of citizen science trainers	Derived or complied	CSV, spreadsheet formats	Using information that is available in other projects about networks and their information	Other people who want to reach out to citizen science training networks	Several MB	Beyond the project, for the operations of the European Citizen Science Academy
WP5 (SfC) Inclusivity in Citizen Science	Taxonomy of information gathered through pre and post-event assistance survey	Demographics, personal data, event feedback	<p>Filled electronic forms with paper backup versions if necessary (digitised afterwards)</p> <p># Demographics: Name Surname Gender Identity Age Nationality Level of education Disabilities (perception) Stakeholder type Name of Organisation (if any)</p>	N/A	Research about the need for further initiatives and projects tackling inclusiveness issues in CS.	-100Kb	Lifetime of the project

WP and partner responsible for the data, activity of data collection	Short data description, aim of the data and relevance for the project	Type of data	Data format	Reuse of any existing data	Relevance outside the project	Expected size	Storage period
			Economic background Previous knowledge on CS # Qualitative Expectations regarding the event attended Event feedback Personal views on inclusiveness in CS				
WP6 (ECSA) Subscribers to the ECS newsletter	This dataset consists of subscribers to the ECS newsletter to inform about project progress. It contains names and addresses of those that opted in.	Observational, Event-related	Mailchimp email list with names	The newsletter (and associated mailchimp) of the EU-Citizen.Science project has been taken over. Its subscriber data is staying within ECSA and is going to be re-used for the ECS newsletter.	N/A, this data is confidential.	N/A	Beyond the project. Newsletter subscribers can opt out of the newsletter anytime.

WP and partner responsible for the data, activity of data collection	Short data description, aim of the data and relevance for the project	Type of data	Data format	Reuse of any existing data	Relevance outside the project	Expected size	Storage period
WP6 (ECSA) Data about communication and dissemination activities	Visuals describing communication and dissemination activities	Observational, Event-related	.PDF Photo formats Video formats Audio formats	Using visual material available from other projects or networks	Other individuals, projects, organisations interested in citizen science and related topics	Several 100 MB Video files: several 100 GBs	> 3 years Licence creative commons
WP6 (NMC) Data for the SWOT analysis and development of the business model in T6.4	We will conduct interviews and workshops with the WP leaders and Consortium Partners to develop a business model	Observational, Event-related	.DOCX	Data from public deliverables produced in the EU-Citizen.Science project	Not relevant outside the project	Not more than 1 GB	Lifetime of the project
WP7 (MfN)	We will conduct a national stakeholder mapping exercise to identify opportunities and gaps for developing links with CS and Open Science. Based on this, we will co-design recommendations for and with policymakers and funders to strengthen support for CS initiatives in Europe and update the	Observational, Derived/Compiled, Event-related	Spreadsheet, forms, metadata in CSV, spreadsheet formats	Not foreseen	The data generated will strengthen the recognition of CS as a policy-making tool and as a valuable research approach for scientific excellence and sustainable development in Europe.	Several MB	Lifetime of the project + 3 years

WP and partner responsible for the data, activity of data collection	Short data description, aim of the data and relevance for the project	Type of data	Data format	Reuse of any existing data	Relevance outside the project	Expected size	Storage period
	version of the CS SDG Declaration to be presented at high-level political events.						
WP8 (ZSI) Data for evaluation and impact assessment – internal data	Data collected from project partners to demonstrate impact in each predefined impact area. Depending on target groups, planned activities, expected impacts and connected indicators, different data types will be collected.	Observational, Event-related	.XMLX/.CSV .DOCX .PDF Photo formats Video formats Audio formats Extracts from Miro, Padlet, Canva, etc.	Not foreseen	Demonstrating the effectiveness of Citizen Science initiatives. Exchanging impact assessment frameworks and methodologies.	Several 100 MB Video files: several 100 GBs	Lifetime of the project +3 years Published data (video recordings on YouTube) beyond the lifetime of the project
WP8 (ZSI) Data for evaluation and impact assessment – external data	Data collected from other CSIs to demonstrate impact. Data types depend on target groups, activities and formats.	Observational, Event-related	.XMLX/.CSV .DOCX .PDF Photo formats Video formats Audio formats Extracts from Miro, Padlet, Canva, etc.	Potentially in collaboration with other CS initiatives	Demonstrating the effectiveness of Citizen Science initiatives. Exchanging impact assessment frameworks and methodologies.	Several 100 MB Video files: several 100 GBs	Lifetime of the project +3 years Published data (video recordings on YouTube) beyond the lifetime of the project

WP and partner responsible for the data, activity of data collection	Short data description, aim of the data and relevance for the project	Type of data	Data format	Reuse of any existing data	Relevance outside the project	Expected size	Storage period
Informed Consent sheets (of all WPs and activities) (all partners)	Online events might be recorded and shared on YouTube. Informed Consent sheets/forms will be distributed to event participants, collected by the event organising partner/affiliated entity and stored locally.	Observational, Event-related	.DOCX .PDF Hardcopies	Not foreseen	N/A	Several MB	Lifetime of the project +3 years

2. FAIR data

FAIR data means that the data is **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable, and **R**eusable.

Digital tools and skills for FAIR and open science are key enablers for the implementation of the new European Research Area, enhancing collaboration that will in turn accelerate research and innovation, as well as increase trust in science to be conducted with and for society (EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group 2021). The EC report “Turning FAIR into Reality” (European Commission DG Research and Innovation 2018) concludes that FAIR digital objects (including software) need to be supported by FAIR services that provide persistent identifiers, metadata specifications, stewardship and repositories, actionable policies and Output Management Plans. All of these need to be created for FAIR software, to complement the significant FAIR initiatives that primarily encompass data, and to leverage existing efforts to enable this for software.

ECS will follow the FAIR principles of data sharing for data use during the course of the project and beyond as described in the following sections.

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The following actions will be taken to make data findable:

- I. data and metadata will be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier, a DataCite Digital Object Identifier (DOI);
- II. data will be described with rich standard metadata in multiple human- and machine-readable formats (defined by the reusable principles);
- III. metadata will clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes; and
- IV. data and metadata will be registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

The repository that will be used, Zenodo, offers version tracking. Deliverable reports will have a data identification sheet and version log.

ECS will follow open standard formats and coherent name filing conventions to endorse the FAIR principles of data sharing. Formats used in ECS should be suited for long-term preservation and accessibility and therefore be commonly used, have open specifications and be independent of specific software, developers or suppliers. Some examples of acceptable formats are: .XLM, .DOCX, .XLSX, .PPTX, .PDF, .CSV, photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG), video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .MOV, .AVI), Audio format (.MP3, .MP4), HTML or other coding language.

The data generated in ECS will adhere to good research practice by implementing specific naming and versioning protocols – useful in collaborative projects. A version control system will be employed to ensure the data is properly arranged, allowing to keep track of various versions of the datasets. This type of control system, also known as a revision control system, records the incremental modifications (revisions) of files over a period of time.

Labelling of files in a systematically structured way to ensure the coherence of the final dataset will be done by following a common labelling format as recommended:

- For deliverables: ECS_DX.X_Title. Where “X.X” is the deliverable number, “Title” is the deliverable title. To label the different working version “_vY.Y” will be added at the end of the file name, where “Y” is the version number using 00 for the draft, 01 for the first version and 1.0 for the final version.

- For other files: ECS_Title or if they belong to a specific WP ECS_WPX_Title, following the same convention of adding “_vY.Y” to identify the different working versions when needed.

2.2. Making data accessible

Access to non-personal collected data and all developed digital methods will be open and free via the project platform (<https://eu-citizen.science/>) and repositories such as [Zenodo](#) (the recommended repository by the EU OpenAIRE initiative and hosted at the European Organisation for Nuclear Research (CERN)) or [GitHub](#).

Zenodo automatically assigns a DOI (digital object identifier) to a dataset once the entire deposit procedure has been completed. Data and metadata that will be made openly available will have a unique identifier, e.g. a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), and will be retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol. This protocol will be open, free, universally implementable, and will allow for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.

All code related to WP3 activities is openly available and will be in the future. The services created under the Cos4Cloud project that will be used in the datathon and hackathon in WP3 are also open, e.g. MECODA has been released under EUPL.

The eu-citizen.Science platform code is available on GitHub under European Union Public License 1.2 (EUPL). This is a copyleft free/open source software licence created on the initiative of and approved by the European Commission. Information about the Permissions, Limitations and Conditions of this licence as well as the licence itself can be found in the LICENSE file of the repository:

- https://github.com/lbercivis/EU-CS_platform
- https://github.com/lbercivis/EU-CS_platform/blob/master/LICENSE

ECS will share all relevant knowledge developed in the project with actors including citizens, civil society, and end users by making available all the services, tools, training materials, open educational resources, policy recommendations and other project results on eu-citizen.science platform and the CSDA (Citizen Science Data Academy). Project deliverables, reports, presentations, workshop contents, datasets etc. will be deposited on [Zenodo](#) and linked to a ‘Zenodo community’ named after the project for easy access. Recordings of public events will be shared and made available on the ECSA YouTube channel. Pictures and videos of participants will only be taken with explicit permission from participants.

Personal data will remain with the respective partners responsible for the activities, will be stored locally and not shared with others, with the exception of project contact lists for internal communication. A contact list with names and email addresses of consortium members is stored on the project Google Drive which is only shared with consortium members¹. Personal data will – if at all – only be published in aggregated form and anonymised properly, for example to report participation in dissemination events (total participants, participants per stakeholder group, newcomers to citizen science, etc.). The analysis of the data for statistical and communication purposes will be carried out on de-identified or anonymised data.

At the end of the project, all non-anonymous data will be deleted unless explicit consent was given to the partner or affiliated entity who collected the data to store the data after the project.

¹ Access to the shared project folder on Google Drive and to documents in the shared project folder only granted to known colleagues in the project and administrators of partner organisations and affiliated entities.

As per the specific rules laid out in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement, project partners must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. Therefore, publications of project results stemming from ECS will be published in top journals, ensuring free accessibility by publishing in Gold Open Access and/or using the Open Research Europe publication platform.

2.3. Making data interoperable

The research datasets as well as associated metadata and documentation will be compliant to international standards in order to guarantee easy interoperability and re-use. Open file formats will be preferred and the consortium will apply widely-used controlled vocabularies as needed. Metadata on the eu-citizen.science platform is following standards (e.g. [PPSR Core on Citizen Science projects](#)) which allow the interoperability with similar platforms.

In case it is unavoidable to use uncommon vocabularies and the project generated its own specific vocabulary, mappings to more commonly used ontologies/vocabularies or additional explanations will be provided together with the data in order to allow interoperability across disciplines and to allow reusing, refining and extending them.

The following actions will be taken to make data interoperable:

- I. data and metadata will use an accessible, shared, and broadly applicable programming language;
- II. data and metadata will use standard, globally controlled vocabularies that follow FAIR principles;
- III. data and metadata will include qualified references to other data and metadata; and
- IV. data and metadata will be published in formats ensuring interoperability.

2.4. Increase data re-use

The following actions will be taken to promote the reusability of data:

- I. data and metadata will be richly described with multiple accurate and relevant attributes;
- II. data and metadata will be released with a clear and accessible data usage licence (e.g. CCO, the default waiver for distributing open data or Data Use Agreements when data will be restricted due to privacy concerns);
- III. data and metadata will be associated with detailed provenance; and
- IV. data and metadata will meet domain-relevant community standards.

As mentioned in section 2.2, all open data generated in the project will be made available on Zenodo, GitHub, the eu-citizen.science platform and by publishing in gold open access.

Whenever the data is stored on an open data repository such as Zenodo, a licence will be specified to clarify the extent of allowed usage. Zenodo provides links to a large number of well-known open licences. Thus, the ECS consortium may decide on an appropriate licence for each data object. Choosing well-known open licences as well as the use of controlled vocabularies ensures re-use of the data. According to Zenodo policy, its lifetime is ensured for the next 20 years (<https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>).

3. Other research outputs

As mentioned in section 2.2, ECS will share all relevant knowledge developed in the project with actors including citizens, civil society, and end users by making available all the services, tools, training materials, open educational resources, policy recommendations and other project results on eu-citizen.science platform and the CSDA (Citizen Science Data Academy). Project deliverables, reports, presentations, workshop contents, datasets etc. will be deposited on [Zenodo](#) and linked to a 'Zenodo community' named after the project for easy access. Recordings of public events will be shared and made available on the ECSA YouTube channel. Pictures and videos of participants will only be taken with explicit permission from participants.

In line with the FAIR principles, project outputs will be made findable by sharing them through the eu-citizen.science platform, GitHub and the project community on Zenodo. Project reports or presentations, among others, stored on Zenodo will also be assigned a DOI and be described with rich metadata in multiple human- and machine-readable formats. In case of project outputs not stored on Zenodo, enough context will be provided on the provenance of the information shared to allow for re-use. These research outputs will also follow open standard formats and coherent name filing conventions.

4. Allocation of resources

Specific rules on the requirements for research data management of Horizon Europe are described in article 17 of the Grant Agreement. These include the definition and execution of a DMP and its regular updating, depositing the data in a trusted repository, and ensuring open access, among others. T1.3 "Data management" in WP1 "Project management and coordination" is led by the project coordinator, ECSA, and partners Ibercivis and CSIC contribute. The work package leaders will manage the data creation and management process for their respective work packages. All other consortium partners are committed to contribute to the data management as generators and collectors of data themselves.

Costs for making ECS research data FAIR are eligible to be covered by the project budget during the official funding period provided they are compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions.

Data archiving on Zenodo and copyright licensing with Creative Commons are free of charge. Zenodo's funding is guaranteed for the next 20 years by public bodies. Thus, no additional costs are expected for preserving the open research data.

Many of the project results and outputs will be made available on the eu-citizen.science platform as mentioned in section 2.2. These include the European Citizen Science Academy and all its training, the Citizen Science Data Academy, the new features of the eu-citizen.science platform and its growing database of projects, resources, etc.

A plan for new business and governance models of the platform will be developed under T6.4 "Exploitation plan and business model". With the implementation of the strategy after the lifetime of the project and the exploitation of project results and platform functionalities, the aim is that the eu-citizen.science platform becomes financially sustainable and a service provider for the citizen science community. This will also ensure long-term preservation of project outputs.

5. Data security

Concerning data security and privacy issues, the DMP will consider the EU directives and national regulations related to both users' rights relating to electronic communications networks and services, to the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector. Under no circumstance will the project include, store or process private information, pictures etc. without the explicit and written permission of the respective persons. Under no circumstance we will provide personal data to third parties.

It is pertinent to distinguish between personal data and non-personal data here.

Non-personal research data from the project is stored on the collaboration space on Google Drive as well as in partners' local machines and dependencies. Access to the shared project folder on Google Drive and to documents in the shared project folder are granted to known colleagues in the project and administrators of partner organisations and affiliated entities managing varying access rights. Moreover, information and documents not containing personal data are shared beyond the ECS consortium with other projects for collaboration (e.g. minutes of joint meetings, presentations, a calendar of meetings) and stored on the shared project folder in subfolders marked as such.

Personal data will be stored safely under the conditions and obligations of GDPR by the partner or affiliated entity who is collecting this kind of data.

Data recovery will be guaranteed by regular data backups of information stored on the shared project folder on Google Drive. Moreover, Google Drive has a versioning service so data can also be restored in case of any accidental deletion. Consortium partners may also store the data they generated on their own secure servers, making sure that secure storage is guaranteed.

As mentioned above, open research data will be shared via Zenodo. Zenodo provides professional data security services detailed [here](#).

Partners and affiliated entities take responsibility for the security of personal data they possess in terms of both physical infrastructure and access policy, ensuring data protection by design and by default.

6. Ethics

The ECS project will collect or generate data from questionnaires, interviews, participatory workshops, discussions, reflection and learning sessions involving stakeholders and citizens that participate voluntarily in the project. **The project will be collecting and processing personal data in these instances.** How these data will be handled has been addressed at different points over the last sections of this DMP. All is collected in the current section.

Any data collection, processing and storage activities, procedures and tools in the project will be in line with the personal data protection and intellectual property rights of the European Union, as defined by the European Commission, and national legislation relevant to the country where the data collection is taking place. Data records containing personal data are managed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679). ECS will not be collecting any 'special categories' of personal data as defined by Article 9 of the GDPR Regulation (EU) 2016/679. Formalised questionnaires and personal data will be stored at the local level.

The ECS consortium shall ensure that data on individuals are transmitted and used in a secure environment; that the use of the data complies with ethical and legal requirements (including signed informed consent and applicable data protection laws); and that the use of both existing and new data is agreed with the data owner/data provider.

In principle, personal data will remain with the respective partner or affiliated entity responsible for the activities carried out in the project, and it will be stored locally and safely under the conditions and obligations of GDPR. As of the beginning of July 2023, ECSA is working on a Joint Controller Agreement for the consortium to formalise how to jointly collect and process personal data between and among several partners and affiliated entities in activities carried out jointly. Unless permission has been explicitly requested from participants in project activities, personal data will not be shared with other partners and affiliated entities in the consortium. The exception is project contact lists of colleagues working in ECS for internal communication within the project – although this is covered by the Consortium Agreement. Under no circumstance will the project include, store or process private information, pictures etc. without the explicit and written permission of the respective persons. Under no circumstance will the project provide personal data to third parties. Personal data will – if at all – only be published in aggregated form and anonymised properly, for example to report participation in dissemination events (total participants, participants per stakeholder group, newcomers to citizen science, etc.). The analysis of the data for statistical and communication purposes will be carried out on de-identified or anonymised data.

Concerning data security and privacy issues, the DMP will consider the EU directives and national regulations related to both users' rights relating to electronic communications networks and services, to the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector.

All activities in the project dealing with personal data will include informed consent procedures (oral where possible and written) providing transparent information about the project, the data collection and/or processing, data storage and deletion, and rights to update or delete personal data complying with GDPR. A standardised process for collecting informed consent in the project activities will be followed. Informed consent (forms, sheets or questionnaires including it) will be collected by the partner or affiliated entity implementing the activity and stored locally for up to three years after the end of the project – these are indicated as one dataset in Table 3.

It is not planned for participation in the project actions to involve children/minors. The ECS project will adapt to needs as they arise and the DMP being regularly updated and adapted to project developments will do so too. While there are not currently any plans to engage minors, in case the project does engage younger people, the ECS ethics procedures will be adapted to comply with standard procedures to involve minors in project activities and informed consent forms for children and parents/guardians will be necessary and provided to the consortium. Collection, processing and storage of personal data of minors would be GDPR-compliant.

Overall, the project policy to deal with personal data is that it is only collected with the explicit, informed consent and voluntary agreement of the participants, not collected for purposes beyond the project's aims, collected only as necessary and deleted in case it was collected unintentionally.

An internal ethics working group is being created in the project that will address issues related to ethics in data collection and management as they arise.

7. Outlook

As mentioned in the introduction of the document, this DMP will be updated and adapted as the project evolves and develops. Upcoming iterations might provide more detail on the data erasure policy, and archiving and preservation of data.

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